

EFFECT OF LOCAL CASSAVA FERMENTATION METHODS ON FUNCTIONAL,
PASTING AND SENSORY PROPERTIES OF *LAFUN*

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ABSTRACT

The effects of two fermentation methods (fixed and unfixed methods) and fermentation periods (48h, 72h, 96h) on the HCN content, texture, colour, flavour, water retention capacity, bulk density and rheological properties of *lafun* were studied. Result obtained showed that the HCN content of *lafun* obtained through the method of leaving fermentation water was significantly lower (0.006%-0.004%) than when the fermentation was changed regularly (0.014%-0.010%). On the other hand bulk density and water retention capacity were significantly higher in *lafun* processed by method of leaving the fermentation water constant (bulk density 1.742g/cm³-1.823g/cm³), (water absorption capacity (0.607gg⁻¹- 1.271gg⁻¹). It was also observed that the longer the period of fermentation, the higher the values for the bulk density and water absorption capacity. Texture, appearance and flavour were not significantly different in *lafun* processed from the two fermentation methods but there was a significant difference in the periods used for the fermentation with the ones fermented for longer period being more preferred.

KEYWORDS: Cassava fermentation, *lafun*, HCN content, organoleptic properties

INTRODUCTION

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* crantz) is a major food crop in Nigeria as a cheap calorie source, supplying about 70% of the daily calorie of over 50 million people in Nigeria (Oluwolé *et al.*, 2004). It has also been estimated that cassava provides food for over 500 million people in the world (Abu *et al.*, 2006). It is essentially a carbohydrate food with low protein and fat. Edible part of fresh cassava root contains 32-35% carbohydrate, 2-3% protein, 75-80% moisture, 0.1% fat, fibre and 0.70 - 2.50% ash (Ihekoronye and Ngoddy, 1985; Oluwolé *et al.*, 2004).

However, much attention has continually been drawn to the anti nutritional substance (cyanide) in this crop which could be lethal to man if consumed in large doses over a period of time (Hahn and Keyser, 1985; Hahn, 1989). To make cassava suitable for human consumption, it is usually subjected to different processing methods which vary from location to location. Such methods generally aim at reducing the toxicity, improving palatability and converting the perishable fresh root into stable products. Cassava root is normally processed before consumption as a means of detoxification, preservation and modification and various fermented cassava products are available including 'gari', 'fufu' and 'lafun' (Oyewolé, 1991). 'Lafun' is produced through the submerged fermentation of peeled cassava roots in water (Oyewolé and Odunfa, 1988). After fermentation, the fermented cassava is subjected to sun-drying and milled in order to have 'lafun' flour. The flour is usually turned in boiled water, with no extra heating, and made to a stiff porridge which is consumed with soup. One of the constraints in the commercialization of local fermented cassava products is that the quality of the products varies from one processor to the other and even from one processing batch to the other by the processor (Oyewolé and Sanni, 1995). Factors which have been found to be responsible for this include: the differences in methods of processing from one processor to the other (Akingbala *et al.*, 1991); variations in the temperature of fermentation as influenced by the season (Blansherd *et al.*, 1994), the age and the variety of the cassava root used by different processors (Almazan, 1992; Idowu and Akindele, 1994). In an attempt to improve on its flavour; some modern producers of *lafun* have adapted the "unfixed fermentation" method, which involves changing the water daily throughout the period of fermentations against the previously practiced fixed fermentation method in which the water remains unchanged throughout this period. Presently, there is limited information on the comparative effects of these two methods on the hydrocyanic acid content as well as some

quality attributes such as functional, pasting properties of lafun. Such information could help in standardizing lafun production through public health policy formulation. The present study, therefore, seeks to compare the effect of fixed and unfixed fermentation methods on some quality attributes of lafun using local cultivar of cassava, '*Isunikankoniyan*'. Information is however not available on the effect of local fermentation methods on the quality of 'lafun'. As of date, new cassava varieties are being introduced to farmers for their agronomic benefits (Akoroda *et al.*, 1989; Akingbala *et al.*, 1989), with little considerations for the quality of the end products (Ihedioha *et al.*, 1996; Ijabadeniyi, 2007; Nwabueze and Odunsi, 2007). There is the need to have information on fermentation methods that gives the best quality 'lafun'. These will help to solve the current problem of variations in the quality of 'lafun' produced by various processes and by the same processes at different fermentation batches. This work was embarked upon to study the effect local fermentation methods on proximate, functional and pasting properties of lafun produced from one local variety of cassava.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials: Cassava variety used for this work was a local cassava variety '*Isunikankoniyan*' which were obtained from a local farms in Abeokuta, Nigeria and were about 10-12 months old at the time of harvest.

Processing of cassava tubers for lafun production: The method described by Oyewole and Odunfa (1988) was adopted. The cassava roots were sorted by visual assessment, peeled, washed, divided into two equal parts and soaked submerged in two 50-litre plastic containers for the 96 h-fermentation process under ambient condition ($30\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$). However, in one container, the fermentation water remained unchanged throughout the soaking period (fixed fermentation) whereas in the second container, there was regular changing of water daily throughout the period of fermentation (unfixed fermentation). The resulting retted roots were hand-pulverized to obtain the raw cassava mash. The fermented root was then sun-dried for two days before being milled to flour.

Physicochemical characteristics

Proximate composition: Proximate composition of samples was determined according to the method of (AOAC, 1990) for crude protein, crude fat, ash, moisture and fibre respectively. Carbohydrate was obtained by difference.

Pasting characteristics: Pasting properties of the flour were characterized by using rapid Visco-analyzer (RVA) as described by Deffenbaugh and Walker (1989) for Peak viscosity, breakdown viscosity, set back, pasting temperature, and final viscosity.

HCN content: Estimation of hydrocyanic acid content was done using silver nitrate volumetric analyses (AOAC, 1990; Oboh *et al.*, 2002; Tanya *et al.*, 1997) for raw cassava mash from the fixed and unfixed methods of fermentation. 10g of each sample was weighed into 300ml round bottle flask and left to soak in water for 4 h. It was then steam distilled into 20 ml of 2.5% (w/v) NaOH contained in an Erlenmeyer flask. The distillation continued until 250 ml of the distillate was collected. 8.0ml of 6N NaOH and 2ml of 5% (w/v) KI were added to the distillate. The distillate was then titrated with 0.02N AgNO_3 until there was a faint but permanent turbidity. Five replicates analyses were performed for each sample.

Bulk density: Cassava mash or lafun was placed in a 25-ml graduated cylinder and packed by gently tapping the cylinder on the bench top for 30 times from a height of 5 cm. This was done three times each for raw mash from the 2 fermentation methods. The bulk density was determined as (Babajide *et al.*, 2008; Nzigamasabo and Hui, 2006; Akubor *et al.*, 2000; Wang and Kinsella, 1976):

Water retention capacity: Four grams of the lafun sample and 20 ml of distilled water were put into a 50 ml centrifuge tube. The mixture was stirred occasionally with a glass rod for 30 min after which it was centrifuged at 15000 rpm for 15 min. The amount of water retained by the cassava mash or lafun sample was taken as the difference between the initial water added and that decanted after centrifugation (Benchat, 1977).

Titrateable acidity and pH: Titrateable acidity and pH were assessed using the method of Lees (1975), while the procedures described by Dubois *et al.*, (1956) was followed for the starch and free sugar analysis.

Sensory Analysis

The fermented cassava flour ('lafun') was cooked by turning the flour in boiled water (flour /water ratio of 1:4). The water was brought to boil on a gas cooker in a pot. The flame was put off and the cassava flour was poured into the boiled water with some aggressive turning using a local turning stick. The flour was turned to form a thick paste of consistent appearance. Sensory evaluation was carried out within ten minutes of preparation. A ten man trained sensory panel was raised from among the local consumers of 'lafun'. The panelists were familiar with the scoring scale and the assessment method during the preliminary training session. The samples were arranged randomly and presented to the judges in the same type of plates and each sample was coded in such a way that the panelists could not be biased by the coding system as a set of three digits of random numbers were assigned to each sample. A ten point hedonic scale was used for the evaluation of the degree of preference of the appearance, smoothness, taste, texture and non-stickiness of the products, with "0" indicating worst preference for the product on the attribute and "10" indicating highest preference. The means of their scores were used to determine the most preferred method for 'lafun' production.

Data analysis: Data obtained were subjected to students't-test analyses in all cases.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the result of the proximate composition for the fixed and unfixed fermented lafun flour. The result of the proximate analysis carried out on lafun samples showed that the protein content of the samples whose fermentation water was changed regularly(unfixed)(2.00-2.40%) was higher than that which the water remain constant(fixed)(1.78-1.99%) which shows that the longer the fermentation hours, the more reduced the protein content. The fat content ranged between (0.20- 0.30%) for unfixed fermentation while fixed fermentation had value ranged from 0.22 to 0.26%. The ash content follow the same trend with value ranged between (0.92-1.12%) for fixed fermentation and (1.00 – 1.14%) for unfixed fermentation. These reductions had earlier been reported to be due to combination of leaching into the soaking water and microbial utilization (Oyewole and Odunfa, 1999). This mean that the longer the cassava stay in the fermenting water, the more the minerals are leached into the water thereby making them to have reduced values of protein an ash. Fermentation also effected lower reduction in the starch contents of cassava used for the lafun production (70.46%-74.37%).

Table1: Proximate composition of lafun produced from fixed and unfixed fermentation methods

	Protein	starch	Ash	Fat	Fibre
Fixed fermentation					
48h	1.99±0.01	71.64±0.04	1.12±0.01	0.26±0.01	1.45±0.01
72h	1.90±0.01	73.61±0.03	1.05±0.01	0.24±0.01	1.42±0.05
96h	1.78±0.01	75.67±0.02	0.92±0.01	0.22±0.01	1.38±0.02
Unfixed fermentation					
48h	2.40±0.01	70.46±0.01	1.14±0.01	0.30±0.01	1.25±0.04
72h	2.11±0.01	72.41±0.01	1.11±0.01	0.28±0.01	1.22±0.01
96h	2.00 ±0.01	74.37±0.01	1.00±0.01	0.20±0.01	1.20±0.05

PHYSIO-CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

The result of the physicochemical properties of lafun produced from fixed and unfixed fermentation methods were shown in Table 2. The fermentation methods used are characterized by increased acid production (increase in total titratable acidity and decrease in pH). Fixed fermentation method produced higher titratable acidity with values ranging from 10.26 to 16.56 while unfixed fermentation gave lower titratable acidity with value ranging from 9.36 to 15.77. This implies that the more the cassava stays in the water during fermentation, the more there is reduction in their pH by the action of micro-organism. Acid production during cassava fermentation has been attributed to the activities of the lactic acid bacteria on the carbohydrate content of cassava root (Oyewole and Afolami, 2000).

Bulk density is an indication of the porosity of a product which influences packages design and has been found to be a function of flour wettability (Solsuki, 1962). According to Padmasshree *et al.*, (1987), higher bulk density is desirable for greater ease of dispersibility of flours. There is slight increase in bulk density of lafun from fixed fermentation process over that from unfixed fermentation is an indication that lafun from the former may contain more fibre contents than that from the latter. This possibly resulted from increased particle breakdown of the fibrous materials during fermentation, enabling the fibre to pass along with the pulp during

sieving. Mathew *et al.* (1995) and Nzigamasabo and Hui (2006) reported that fermenting micro organisms elaborate pectinolytic and cellulotic enzymes, which facilitate the lysis of the cell membranes. The insoluble fibre is thus disintegrated during the lytic process and automatically passes along the pulp.

The water retention capacity of a starch granule gives the degree of exposure of the internal structure of the starch granules to water (Niba *et al.*, 2001; Raules *et al.*, 1993). It is an important processing parameter and has implication for viscosity, bulking and consistency of product as well as baking applications (Kulkarni *et al.*, 1991; Niba *et al.*, 2001). In this study, the water retention capacity was affected by the method of fermentation. Cassava fermented without changing the water (fixed) has higher water retention capacity than the cassava whose water was changed (unfixed). This suggests that the internal structure of the starch granule may have been exposed to a greater extent during fermentation period, perhaps as a result of the increased activity of the micro-organism. Also, since water retention capacity is related to bulking, this possibly explains in addition to other factors considered earlier, why the cassava whose water was not changed during fermentation recorded high bulk density than the one whose water was changed regularly; this result was in agreement with study reported by Tanya *et al.*, 2006). As the period of fermentation increased, the bulk density and water retention capacity also increased.

Swelling index is a measure of the ability of starch to imbibe water and swell. The values ranged from 26.75-27.63% for unfixed fermentation while the values for fixed fermentation ranged from 28.73 to 31.63%. The lafun samples were significantly different in their swelling power.

Sanni *et al.* (2001) reported that the swelling index of granules reflect the extent of associative forces within the granules therefore the higher the swelling index, the lower the associative forces. The cyanide contents of both fixed and unfixed fermented lafun flour were significantly lowered ($p < 0.05$) when the fermentation water remained unchanged throughout the fermentation period, compared to when the fermentation water was changed daily (Table 2). The value of cyanide obtained is below the lethal dose of 40-60 mg/kg as reported by Bokanga (1994). This value is significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than the 0.35 obtained from unfixed fermentation. The difference may be attributable the texture, colour and flavour of lafun which is due to the increased concentration of micro organisms in the fixed fermentation which hastens the breakdown of cyanogenic glycoside as reported by Oyewole and Odunfa (1990). The percentage of HCN loss followed the same trend. Highest percentage loss of HCN was recorded by the sample that was fermented for 96 hours without changing of the water. This implied that the sample had enough time for their cyanide bond to be hydrolyzed as it has been reported earlier that the importance of fermentation in cassava processing is based on its ability to reduce the cyanogenic glycosides to relatively insignificant levels (Omonigho and Ikenebomeh, 2002; Oyewole and Afolami, 2000; Okoro and Isa 2003). Therefore, leaving the fermentation water unchanged throughout the fermentation period gave better result in terms of the HCN content.

Table 2: Physicochemical characteristics of lafun produced from fixed and unfixed fermentation

	pH	TTA	HCN	Bulk density	WAC	Swelling index	Sugar
Fixed fermentation							
48h	5.10	10.26	0.92	1.74	0.61	28.73	0.48
72h	4.33	12.96	0.27	1.81	0.82	30.74	0.51
96h	3.66	16.56	0.16	1.82	1.34	31.63	0.55
Unfixed fermentation							
48h	5.72	9.36	1.01	1.65	0.57	26.75	0.40
72h	4.83	13.37	0.78	1.73	0.78	27.23	0.44
96h	3.87	15.77	0.35	1.79	1.27	27.63	0.48

TTA: Total titratable acid; HCN: Hydro-cyanide acid; WAC: Water absorption capacity

PASTING PROPERTIES

Table 1 shows the pasting properties of lafun produced from fixed and unfixed fermentation methods. The final viscosity ranged from 356.05RVU to 348.24RVU for unfixed fermented lafun while the cassava that was fermented for 48hrs without changing the water has the least value of 327.60RVU. There is a significant difference in the final viscosity of the lafun samples. Shimelis *et al.* (2006) reported that final viscosity is used to indicate the ability of starch to form various paste or get after cooling and that less stability of starch paste is commonly accompanied with high value of breakdown. This implied that starch paste from unfixed fermented

lafun which has the highest for final viscosity will be less stable after cooling compared to the other samples, hence retrogradation will occur faster. The variation in the final viscosity might be due to the simple kinetic effect of cooling on viscosity and the re-association of starch molecules in the samples (Ikegwu *et al.*, 2009). Result of the set back viscosity of the starch samples ranged between (166.45RVU-149.96RUV) for fixed fermentation with sample fermented for 48h having the highest value of 166.45 RVU while unfixed fermented lafun for 96h had the lowest value of 149.90RVU. There are no significant differences in the set back viscosities of the lafun produced from both fixed and unfixed fermentation methods. Sanni, *et al* (2001) reported that lower set back viscosity during the cooling of lafun indicate higher resistance to retrogradation. This means that lafun fermented for 48hrs without changing the water will exhibit higher resistance to retrogradation. Pasting temperature also increased as the length of fermentation increases irrespective of the method used. Pasting temperature gives an indication of the gelatinization time during processing. It is the temperature at which the first detectable viscosity is measured and an index characterized by initial change due to the swelling of starch. Pasting temperature has been reported to relate to water binding capacity, a higher pasting temperature implies higher water binding capacity, higher gelatinization and lower swelling property of starch due to high degree of association between starch granules (Ezeala, 1984; Oyewole, 1990).

Table 3: Pasting characteristics of Lafun produced from fixed and unfixed fermentation methods

	Pasting Temp.	Set back	Pasting Time	Final viscosity
Fixed fermentation				
48h	79.35±00	166.45±05	5.42±03	327.61±00
72h	79.84±01	165.47±02	5.28±01	335.63±03
96h	79.93±02	165.43±03	6.93±03	336.11±01
Unfixed fermentation				
48h	82.29±04	150.13±03	4.16±05	348.24±02
72h	83.11±01	149.98±03	4.21±01	349.70±00
96h	83.45±01	149.90±00	5.76 ±02	356.05±05

Results are means of duplicate samples ± S.D

SENSORY EVALUATION

Consumer preference for the cooked lafun made by subjecting the cassava to different methods and periods of fermentation are shown in Table 5. Lafun consumers describe good quality lafun as one with little or no odour, having a characteristics white colour with good texture which does not stick to the hand of the consumers. The preference of the panelist for the characteristic texture, flavour and colour of lafun fermented without changing of water is evident in Table 4, even though these values were not significantly different ($p>0.05$) from those obtained with regular changing of water.

CONCLUSION

In summary, results obtained in this study show that the 2 fermentation methods used here do not really show any significant effect on the texture, flavour and colour of lafun but they do affect the HCN content, bulk density and water retention capacity. Fixed fermentation method, where water is unchanged throughout the fermentation period, is therefore recommended for the production of good quality lafun when using the local cassava cultivar.

Table 4: Sensory evaluation of cooked lafun from fixed and unfixed fermentation methods

SAMPLE CODE	APPEARANCE	PARAMETERS			OVERALL ACCEPTANCE
		TEXTURE	TASTE		
F48	6.50	4.55	4.25		5.6
F72	6.55	4.70	4.25		5.5
F96	6.65	4.75	4.55		5.6
U48	5.00	4.05	4.01		5.2
U72	5.20	4.10	4.12		5.2
U96	5.25	4.25	4.20		5.5

F48: Lafun fermented for 48h without changing water, F72: Lafun fermented for 72h without changing water, F96: Lafun fermented for 96h without changing water, U48: Lafun fermented for 48h with changing of water, U72: Lafun fermented for 72h with changing of water U96: Lafun fermented for 96h with changing of water

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